

Delineation of Geological Structures Using Aeromagnetic Data: A Case of Obokun Local Government Area, Southwestern Nigeria

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Abstract

The geological structures of Obokun Local Government Area, Osun State, Nigeria, were delineated using aeromagnetic data. These structures control the topography, size, spacing, orientation, and shape of the hills, ridges, valleys, and drainage system of the area. The research area is located within the Ilesha Schist Belt, in the southwestern part of Nigeria's Basement Complex, with low-to-medium-grade metasediments, closely related to subordinate mafic bodies and frequently surrounded by migmatite-gneiss suite rocks. The investigation involved the abstraction of the aeromagnetic data of the study area from a larger dataset. The dataset was improved by applying aeromagnetic method filtering techniques such as reduction to the equator (RTE) and analytical signal (AS) on Oasis Montaj version 6.4.2 software. The study groups the magnetic anomaly signatures into three categories: low (11.2–65.2 nT), intermediate (69.2–113.1 nT), and high (125.1–197.9 nT) magnetic intensities, all of which are associated with features of contracting basement rocks. The lineaments inferred are of shallow depth, trending from the northeastern to southwestern parts of the study area. The analytical depth map revealed that the depth of a shallow causative body is between 73 and 147.2 m, and that of a high causative body is between 396 and 1051.8 m. The THDR assisted in delineating most of the geologic structures in the area and in detecting that the rocks are striking northeast-southwest, generally in accordance with the major structural trend of the Basement Complex of Nigeria.

Keywords: Aeromagnetic Data, Geological Structures, Magnetic Intensity, Mapping.

1.0 Introduction

Several organizations have used aeromagnetic survey in many countries, including Nigeria. The survey is capable to map strongly magnetic basements at the regional scale, identify weakly magnetic sedimentary contacts at the local scale, and to search for oil and gas. Subtle lithological connections and intra-sedimentary faults have been located using aeromagnetic data [1, 2].

Modern geophysics relies heavily on airborne geophysical surveys because they cover broad areas more quickly and often at a lower cost than ground surveys [3]. High-resolution surveys are utilised to look at basement trends and intra-formational structures, while potential field methods were first used in the petroleum industry to map the thickness of sedimentary basins [4].

Faults, lithological boundaries, networks of joints, fractures, and sheared zones are structural features in crystalline Basement Complex rocks create homogeneities in the earth's upper crust. Geologic structures control topography, the size, spacing, orientation, and shape of the hill, ridges, valleys, basins, and drainage system [5].

Numerous scholars have used geological and geophysical methods to map certain important geologic features and define lithologies. In order to study subsurface geology, geophysical mapping entails obtaining measurements at or close to the earth's surface. This involves using suitable tools to measure the physical qualities of the regions of the earth that are hidden from direct observation, usually either on or below the surface [6]. These measurements, influenced by the internal distribution of the physical qualities of the

underlying lithologies, enable the identification and location of various lithological units and geological formations. Eldosouky et al. [7], Olomo et al. [8], Amosun et al. [9], Oladejo et al. [10], Awoyemi et al. [11], and Osinowo et al. [12] are a few of the researchers that have shown how useful high-resolution aeromagnetic data is for defining and mapping geological structures. The results of this research will provide the general public with an understanding of the litho-boundary and structural patterns within the study area.

2.0 Location and Geology of the Study Area

The study area, Obokun Local Government, located in Osun State, southwestern Nigeria. It lies within the coordinates of $7^{\circ}50'0''N$ and $4^{\circ}42'0''E$ (Figure 1). The study area is in the southwest of Nigeria's Basement Complex, lies within the Ilesha schist band (Figure 2). The schist

belt is primarily made up of low- medium-grade metasediments that are closely linked to subordinate mafic-bodies which are frequently surrounded by migmatite-gneiss suite rocks [13–16]. Other most common rocks in the Obokun Area include granite, gneiss, and amphibolite.

In the center of the area, the granite gneiss with a northerly foliation trend appears as a small band inside the amphibolite [15, 16]. The gneiss rocks in the northern region of Obokun has quartz with alternating, discontinuous biotite streak-like layers and huge, numerous lensoid microcline. Further south, outcrops are found to have more permanent and distinct alternating biotite-rich layers, which displays better banding development. In the further south, there are well-foliated cultivars with significant biotite and hornblende content [15, 16].

Figure 1: (A) Map of Nigeria, (B) Map of Osun State and (C) Base map of the study area

The textural types of amphibolite include huge, banded, and schistose; with varied proportions of platy to sheaf-like aggregates of hornblende which range in colour from bluish-green to yellowish-green. The massive to weakly foliated types are typically dark green and rather coarse-

grained. They are surrounded by a fine-grained matrix of tabular plagioclase with a composition of labradorite and bytownite [15]. However, within the hornblende and plagioclase, quartz, epidote, and actinolite are frequently found poikiloblastic inclusions. Banded samples are

4.0 Results and Discussion

4.1 Total Magnetic Intensity Map

The magnetic intensity of the study area ranges from 11.2 nT (minimum) to 197.9 nT (maximum). The low magnetic zones (L) deep (blue colour-code) appear to be more concentrated in the south-eastern and little concentration in north-western part of the study area with values ranging from 11.2 nT to 65.2 nT, green to yellow colours indicate low to intermediate magnetic anomalies (M), values ranging from 69.2 to 113.1 nT; the high magnetic zones (red/purple colour-code) in the study area trend from northeastern to southwestern part with values ranging from 125.1 to 197.9 nT. The TMI was used to determine the homogeneity of the area. Figure 3 shows that the study area is heterogenous due to distribution of different magnetic anomalies (low, moderate and high) at different parts of the study area.

4.2 Reduction to the Equator (RTE)

The RTE operation was performed on the extracted magnetic anomaly data by determining an inclination, I of -9.809° and a declination, D of -0.870° using the International Geomagnetic Reference Field (IGRF). The Extracted magnetic anomalies from the RTE map ranges in amplitude from -30.1 to 194.7 nT. The low magnetic anomaly (light blue/blue colour) is concentrated in the southeastern part with little concentration in the northwestern part of the study area, having intermediate magnetic anomaly colour of green/yellow which trends from the northeastern part to northwestern part of the study area (Fig. 4). The high magnetic anomaly (red/purple colour) trends from northeastern part to northwestern part of the study area. The RTE map has helped to position the magnetic anomalies in the study area over their sources by inverting the total magnetic intensity anomalies using constraints based on angle of inclination and declination.

L – Low, I – Intermediate and H - High

Figure 3: Total Magnetic Anomaly Intensity Map of the Study Area.

Figure 4: Reduction to Equator Map of the Study Area

The data was not reduced to the pole because the study location is located in a low latitude region where the RTP transformation is unstable, prone to producing inconsistent map quality, and occasionally dominated by artifacts related to declination parallel [17]. The research region has a low angle of inclination, and the output of the RTE in Figure 4 resembles the TMI map of the area in Figure 3.

4.3 First Vertical Derivative

It is used to map edges of bodies because the vertical contact falls on derivative response which may be positive or negative response. Figure 5, depicts the low anomalies which have values ranging from -0.24 to -0.03 nT, intermediate anomalies with values ranging from -0.02 to 0.03 nT, and the high anomalies with intensity values ranging from 0.03 to 0.20 nT. There are geologic contacts which separate low, intermediate and high magnetic responses represented by thick line in Figure 5. Lineaments are observed on the first vertical derivative map with shallow depth, trending from the northeastern to southwestern parts of the study area.

4.4 Second Vertical Derivative Map

Second vertical derivative was performed on the total magnetic intensity data to suppress the regional content of the data and resolve anomalies by giving a better resolution of closely-spaced sources that enhanced shallow (near surface) and suppressing deeper ones. Figure 6 determined the location of the edges of features such as geologic contacts in the study area by mapping the zero (0) contours as they take zero value over such features. The second vertical derivative magnetic anomaly map of the study area shows magnetic intensity which ranges between -0.001 to 0.001 nT/sqm (Fig. 6). High magnetic anomaly (H) is concentrated in every part of the map. The high magnetic anomaly corresponds to the granite and migmatite-gneiss, majorly when compared to the geological map of the area (Figure 2).

Lineament was also observed on the second vertical derivative (represented in thick lines) are of shallow depth, trending from the northeastern to southwestern part of the study area (Figure 6).

Figure 5: First Vertical Derivative Map of the Study Area.

Figure 6: Second Vertical Derivative Map of the Study Area.

4.5 Total Horizontal Derivative Map

Derivatives essentially enhance high frequency anomalies relative to low frequencies. They tend to resolve the edges of bodies better and make

qualitative interpretation easier. Derivatives by their nature amplify noise in the data. These derivatives include; the horizontal derivative (First, second and total order), Vertical derivatives (first and second), tilt derivatives. Total horizontal

derivative filter is an active tool in discovering edges of magnetized structures and it tends to heighten shallow anomalies [18].

The Total Horizontal Derivative (THD) map in Figure 7 shows that the gradients range from 11.2 nT/m to 197.9 nT/m. The THD function gives a peak anomaly dots amidst the low magnetic intensity anomaly around the contacts for magnetic anomalies [19]. The map shows peaks in the Total Horizontal Gradient (THG) anomalies

which are diagnostic of geologic structures (fractures, faults) heterogeneously distributed within the study area. The peaks magnetic intensities observed in the section are mixed with the low magnetic intensity of the local to semi-regional scale. They are not vividly associated with the rock or the lithology boundaries observed on the THDR map. These features were taken to be an indication of fractures, joints, faults, and stress patterns on the immediate subsurface that could inhabit minerals within the study area.

Figure 7: Total Horizontal Derivative Map of the Study Area.

4.6 Regional and Residual Magnetic Anomaly Map

This map displays variation in magnetic intensity which reflects the magnetic susceptibility of the different rocks across the study area. Residualization was achieved by removing the effect of deep-seated sources through the upward continuation of the maps to a height of 5000 m (Figure 8a). Subsequently, the results were subtracted from the observed values to leave the deeper effects. The residual magnetic anomaly map of the study area showed that the dominant low magnetic anomalies (L) trends in the study area are predominant in the northwestern and southeastern parts with values ranging from -99.4 to -17.2 nT (Figure 8b).

Magnetic lows (depicted by blue colour-code) are indication of rocks with relatively low magnetic susceptibility. Magnetic highs (H) with intensity value range of 32.6 to 97.3 nT (represented with thick line) trending from northwestern to southeastern parts of the map (as depicted by pink colour-code) indicates the presence of rocks with relatively high magnetic susceptibility, typical of crystalline basement rocks (granite and migmatite-gneiss). On the other hand, the part dominated by magnetic lows (L) signifies the presence of weathered material such as laterite, overlying the basement rocks. The lineaments showed in first and second vertical derivatives in Figures 5 and 6 respectively are not well pronounced in the residual map because of upward continuation of the maps to a height of 5000 m.

Figure 8a: Regional Magnetic Anomaly Map of the Study Area.

Figure 8b: Residual magnetic anomaly map of the Study Area.

4.7 Analytical Signal Map

The magnetic anomalous zones on the map in Figure 9 are classified as low (<0.03), intermediate (0.03 to 0.10), and high (>0.12). Based on the magnetic amplitude, these three zones are probably associated with zones of weakness. Every area of the map shows the high amplitude response, which trends NE-SW. The intermediate covers substantial area of the map which stretches to the center. Within the research area, low susceptibility is indicated by the low

amplitude anomaly and high susceptibility by the high amplitude anomaly.

Over the borders of magnetic bodies, the analytical signal rises. The analytical signal filter was applied to the RTE grid in order to determine the source positions of the magnetic anomaly, independent of direction, and the residual magnetization of the source effects, which are mostly related to the RTE. The important feature of the analytical signal is its independence from the source's magnetization direction. Furthermore,

there exists a correlation between the magnitude of the analytical signal and the amplitude of magnetization. According to Reeves et al. [20], the thick straight line represents the highest concentrations of mineral deposits in a given location, which are connected with high analytical signal amplitude (ridges of magnetic anomaly). The central and edge portions of the southern

segment of the area, as well as the high analytic signal amplitude running nearly northwest are the most notable features, as depicted in Figure 9. The migmatite rocks which are present in the northwestern, central, and southern regions of the research area, are the high magnetic signatures of the analytical map [21].

Figure 9: Analytic Magnetic Anomaly Map of the Study Area.

4.8 Analytical Depth Map

This is a type of filtering that help to determine the depth to causative body and mapped geological contact. Depth to the source was determined using analytical depth map title axis to determined the depth to low magnetic anomalies, intermediate magnetic anomalies, and high magnetic anomalies. Geological contacts in

the study area were delineated using thick lines (Figure 8b). Analytical depth map is one of the most important filtering processes which are not affected by angle of inclination, angle of declination and remanent magnetization, which requires little or no geological constraints [21]. Figure 10 shows that depth to shallow causative body is between 73 to 147.2 m, and high causative body is between 396 to 1051.8 m.

Figure 10: Analytical depth map of the Study Area.

5.0 Conclusion

Magnetic data filtering was applied to improve the data and to identify features that may be difficult to map litho-structures and litho-boundaries in Obokun Local Government, Osun State, Nigeria. Outcrop regions were identified based on short wavelength (high frequency) magnetic signatures; to represent structures with thick lines in the study area despite their heterogeneous distribution. Based on the residual anomaly map, it was observed that the northwest and southeast edges are dominated by magnetic lows. These lows have a corresponding magnetic intensity, which indicates the presence of weathered materials such as igneous and metamorphic rocks which have a relatively low magnetic susceptibility covering the basement rocks. The amplitude of the high magnetic anomalous zone (>0.12), middle magnetic anomalous zone (0.03 to 0.10), and low magnetic anomalous zone (<0.03) were shown by the analytical signal map results. High analytical signal amplitude (ridges of magnetic anomaly) is connected with the highest concentrations of mineral deposits in the study area. The low magnetic anomaly varies from 73.0 m to 147.2 m, the intermediate magnetic anomaly ranges from 153.0 m to 344.0 m, and the high magnetic anomaly ranges from 396.0 m to 1051.8 m to the bedrock according to the analytical depth map.

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